

Parental Influence and Peer Pressure: College Students' Susceptibility to Alcohol use

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Abstract:- College students are usually in their late adolescence and young adulthood. In this stage of development, excessive alcohol use is frequently observed. In most cases, intense alcohol use is formed by its social environment and interactions, such as parents, family, and peers. Thus, the current study investigated the impact of parental influence and peer pressure on alcohol use among college students. Using an adapted standardized questionnaire, the researchers randomly surveyed 269 students from different courses in San Agustin Institute of Technology. The respondents of this study were selected using a simple random sampling technique. The data collected were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, and multiple regression. The results revealed that college students perceived moderate parental influence, low peer pressure, and low alcohol consumption. Further, parental influence and peer pressure showed a significant association with alcohol use when assessed using correlational analysis. When regressed, parental influence and peer pressure significantly predict alcohol use. Thus, it is worth mentioning that students' drinking patterns are shaped and manifested by their social interactions with peers and parents.

Keywords:- Parental Influence; Peer Pressure; Alcohol use; Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Numerous experts warn that unhealthy alcohol use can harm a person's health and wellness. It is known to cause poor health, disability, and early death [1]. In addition, heavy alcohol consumption has been linked to a range of adverse outcomes, including traffic accidents, violence as both a perpetrator and a victim, unsafe sexual activity, and delinquency [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO)

mentioned that irresponsible alcohol consumption contributes to over 200 diseases and injuries. Recent reports by World Health Organization (WHO) showed that approximately 5.3% of all deaths worldwide, or roughly three million people annually, are attributed to the harmful effects of alcohol-related consumption [3]. In the Philippines, the Online National Electronic Injury Surveillance System (ONEISS) reported that from 2016 to 2018, 10,372 fatal and non-fatal incidents in the Philippines were attributed to alcohol use [4].

The problem of intense alcohol consumption is even prevalent among younger ages. The Department of Health's recent survey showed that four out of ten Filipinos (40.1%) reported drinking alcohol 30 days before the poll, indicating a high consumption level. In one setting or drinking session, half of Filipinos aged 20 to 59 engage in heavy and binge alcohol drinking or drinking alcohol excessively. Regarding gender, men were more excessive drinkers than women, with 51.4% of men and 28.9% of women. One out of three Filipinos or 43.2% of men and 22.9% of women- drink six or more alcohol on a single occasion [5]. Moreover, over one-fifth (18.9%) of young Filipino females and over half (52.1%) of young Filipino boys binge on drinking alcohol [6]. Hence, Food Nutrition and Research Institute's Clinical and Health Survey supported this result. Accordingly, of young Filipinos aged between 10 and 19, 14.9% drink alcohol, with 36.7% of these being underage drinkers. The poll results likewise showed that these youth are also at risk for adverse health effects of alcohol consumption [4].

In the Philippines, most college students are in their late adolescence and early adulthood. In this development period, intense alcohol consumption and other risky behaviors can be seen or observed frequently [7]. The issues are also present among college students in Valencia City, Bukidnon. Students' perceptions of alcohol consumption are shreds of evidence. Students sometimes consume alcohol

with friends and engage in risky behaviors that affect others. These risky behaviors include; driving under the influence of alcohol, going home past curfew hours, exhibiting some indecent behaviors, even teen pregnancy, and forcing others to consume alcoholic beverages. Thus, the researchers believed that it is urgent to conduct this study based on the abovementioned issues to protect college students from binge alcohol drinking and its harmful effect.

Based on the abovementioned issues, the researchers is trying to assess the extent of factors that influence alcohol use among San Agustin Institute of Technology college students. Specifically, the study aims to: (a) identify the level of parental influence, peer pressure, and alcohol use; (b) test the significant relationship and impact of parental influence and peer pressure on alcohol.

A. Parental Influence in Relation to Alcohol use

All age groups consume alcohol more frequently than any other psychoactive drug [7]. In the Philippine culture, alcohol is an integral part of several family and community celebrations and cultural events, so it is easily accessible. Hence young individuals may not view alcohol as a dangerous substance as they usually see their parents and other relatives or people in their environment along with people they idolize consuming it responsibly [8]. Therefore, family and parental conduct are crucial in shaping how young people use alcohol and whether they experience alcohol-related negative consequences [9].

Several researchers determined the crucial role of the parent's involvement in their children's behavior. Some authors suggest that parents involved in their children's lives, communicating openly, modeling responsible behavior, and providing support can help reduce their children's risk of alcohol use and abuse. Parents who monitor their children's activities and whereabouts are more likely to be aware of their children's alcohol use and can intervene if necessary. Monitoring can involve setting rules and boundaries around alcohol use, knowing where their child is going and with whom, and keeping an eye on their child's behavior and mood [10]. Furthermore, parents who talk openly and honestly about alcohol use and its associated risks can help their children make more informed decisions about drinking [11].

Correspondingly, Parents who model responsible drinking behavior can influence their children's attitudes and behaviors around alcohol. For example, parents who avoid excessive drinking, never drive under the influence and prioritize safety can help their children develop similar habits [12]. Lastly, parents who provide emotional support and positive reinforcement can help their children develop self-esteem and a sense of purpose, reducing their propensity to use alcohol as a coping mechanism [2].

Mares et al. [11] discovered that there is a positive association between parental alcohol-related issues and parental communication about alcohol. Subsequently, this parental communication links with less intense alcohol consumption and alcohol-related issues among adolescents.

On the contrary, Lenient parental attitudes about alcohol and parental alcohol-related issues were directly related to more intense alcohol consumption and alcohol-related problems among adolescents. In conclusion, alcohol-specific communication mediates the association between parental alcohol-related issues and excessive adolescent drinking and alcohol-related issues.

The abovementioned study parallels the works of Kask, Markina, and Podana [12], who examined the influence of family factors on intense alcohol consumption among teenagers. In this study, family factors comprised family structure, bonding, supervision, affluence, and adverse life events. Overall, the finding reveals that all family factors were highly correlated with intense alcohol consumption among teenagers.

The study of Kim and Neff [13] also attested to the direct and indirect effects of parental influence on alcohol use among adolescents. The result revealed substantial links between parental monitoring and adolescent alcohol use. Moreover, the association between parental monitoring and teenage alcohol consumption was mediated by peer influence, perceived alcohol norms, and traditional ties. Findings show that parental participation and proactive parenting style are vital components of preventive and intervention programs targeting teenage alcohol consumption.

The results presented above support the assertion made by Shin, Lee, Lu, and Hecht [10], who found that certain parental factors can predict alcohol use among youth. Specifically, the authors noted that the degree to which parents communicate with their children about alcohol-related issues and monitor their behavior prevents their likelihood of consuming alcohol.

Another study that confirms the association between parental influence and alcohol use was the proposition of [2]. The paper intended to determine the link between parenting style and drunkenness to adolescent drinking. In summary, both binge and non-binge drinking among teenagers correlate with non-authoritative parenting style and parental drunkenness. Furthermore, the non-authoritative parenting style contributes more when compared to parental drunkenness among adolescents' binge drinking.

B. Peer Pressure in Relation to Alcohol use

Social influences, particularly peer relationships, are among the most significant and consistent factors related to college students' intense alcohol use [14]. Peers play a central role in the social context of college students. The impact of peer influence is a more robust college life that can foster positive or negative development in their pre-adulthood life, including substance abuse (e.g., cigarettes, alcohol, and drugs) [15].

Peer pressure is "any attempt by one or more peers to compel an individual to follow in the decisions or behaviors favored by the pressuring individual or group." [1]. In other

words, peer pressure is a term used to describe the subjective experience of being forced, persuaded, or dared to do something by others only because of that people's expectations. [16].

In the case of alcohol use among college students, peer pressure contributes a significant part to the decision of the students in alcohol drinking intentions. Research has shown that college students are particularly susceptible to peer pressure regarding alcohol use. Many college students feel that drinking is an essential part of the college experience, and they may feel pressure from their peers to drink in social situations [7]. College students may experience alcohol-related peer pressure in the form of being offered a toast, having a drink refilled without asking, getting taunted for not drinking, being encouraged to drink more, or being asked to purchase rounds. In addition, some students think drinking within a group is not an individual choice but an obligation to group harmony and loyalty to others within the group [16] [17].

Avoiding peer pressure can be difficult, particularly turning down requests may damage your social status or relationships. To prevent this, choosing carefully the people you associate with can be helpful. While drinking alcohol can be a common and enjoyable social activity that may help reduce stress, it can also be dangerous if not approached responsibly [15]. Therefore, it is essential for those who choose to drink to do so responsibly and respect the choices of those who do not want to consume [1].

However, not all individuals are pressured by their peers. Several experts stipulated that some students resist peer influence. The first reason is that students who hold high self-confidence and self-esteem are more likely to make decisions based on their values and beliefs rather than conform to the opinions and behaviors of their peers [18]. Second, the presence of solid parental and adult role models who provide guidance and support. Students who have positive relationships with their parents or other adult mentors are likelier to seek their advice and trust their judgment when making decisions [10] [19]. Third, students with a strong sense of identity and purpose are less likely to be swayed by peer pressure. When students have a clear understanding of their goals and values, they are more likely to make choices that align with those beliefs and less likely to be influenced by the opinions and actions of others [20] [21]. Lastly, students educated about the dangers and consequences of certain behaviors, such as drug and alcohol use, are better equipped to resist peer pressure. When students have a clear understanding of the risks associated with certain activities, they are more likely to make informed decisions based on their own best interests [22] [23].

The study by Studer et al. [7] proved the crucial role of peer pressure, peer involvement, and peer conformity in developing and continuing alcohol use and misuse among young men in Swiss. Their results showed that peer pressure to misconduct was linked with intense alcohol consumption,

whereas peer involvement and peer conformity were correlated with less alcohol consumption.

The discoveries are likewise parallel to the findings of Monaci et al. [16]. Their study principally determined the effect of peer pressure on alcohol consumption with a moderating influence on emotional intelligence. The results undeniably confirmed that peer pressure predicts alcohol use among university students.

Another study that supports the influence of peer pressure on alcohol use is the findings of Ding et al. [17]. The paper aimed to evaluate the influence of peer pressure and self-efficacy on alcohol use. Through path analysis, the results showed a direct effect of peer pressure on the drinking frequency of the students. Moreover, the finding also confirmed an indirect effect of peer pressure on drinking through self-efficacy related to alcohol self-regulation.

Lastly, Trucco, Colder, and Wieczorek [24] found an association between peer delinquency and alcohol use among adolescents. The authors highlighted that delinquent peer groups are characterized by rebellion against adult authority, rule-breaking, and premature adoption of adult roles, all of which influence the initiation of drinking and high alcohol consumption.

II. METHODS

A. Research Design

The study adopted a quantitative, non-experimental research methodology employing descriptive-correlational techniques. This approach strongly emphasizes statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis and goal estimations based on surveys. It analyzes data statistically to assess a phenomenon [25] [26].

B. Research Local and Participants

The survey was done among the college students of San Agustin Institute of Technology. The sole Catholic tertiary school founded in Valencia City, Bukidnon. For more than 60 years, the school has offered services and programs for both basic and higher education. Because of the intensity of alcohol consumption at this point, the researchers focus on college students. On the other hand, the sample for the current study was determined using probability sampling or random sampling. Using the Raosoft calculator, the researchers selected 269 participants at random from an overall sample of 894.

C. Research Instruments

In order to ensure that the instruments used in the data collection met the criteria for appropriateness, objectivity, and sufficiency to fit in this study's context and to ensure the survey questionnaire's reliability and validity, the researchers went through a number of activities and procedures.

- *Parental influence* is one of the independent variables of the present study, which questionnaire is adapted from the works of Ethen [27]. The instruments were composed of 7-item statements answered on a 5-point Likert scale, with five as strongly agree and one as strongly disagree.
- *Peer Pressure* is another independent variable of the study, which instrument is adapted from the proposition of Ding et al. [14]. The instrument was contextualized and consisted of 10-item statements answered on a 5-point Likert scale with five as strongly agree and one as strongly disagree.
- *Alcohol Use* is the dependent variable of the current study. The instrument called the *Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT)*, a 10-item screening tool developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) [6] to assess alcohol consumption, drinking behaviors, and alcohol-related problems, was used for this variable.

D. Research Local and Participants

Researchers ensured that they adhered to ethical protocols throughout the research. Permission from the Dean, Program Head, research adviser, and respondents' consent were sought at the onset of the study. They have also informed the respondents of the study's objectives and any potential risks associated with the conduct of the study. Participants were encouraged to participate in the research but were never compelled to do so if they refused. In other words, the researchers ensured that all respondents who answered the questionnaires participated in the study voluntarily.

Furthermore, the researchers ensured that the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' personal information were observed. No personal information from the respondents was divulged; besides, no data in the study was falsified and fabricated. Any deceit was avoided, and to ensure the originality of the work, the researchers had their manuscripts examined by plagiarism software. All these ethical issues were avoided to develop a quality and ethically-bound study.

III. RESULTS

A. Descriptive Results of Parental Influence

Shown in Table 1 is the level of parental influence of the respondents, with a total mean of 2.90 and a standard deviation of 0.79, described as "sometimes." This means that the parental influence level of the college students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT) is moderate. However, it must be noted that the item, "Do you feel you are likely to do what your parent(s)/guardian(s) say?" got the highest mean of 3.63, with a standard deviation of 1.19 described as "often," which means high. Meanwhile, "Do you buy alcoholic beverages frequently?" got the lowest mean of 1.83 with a standard deviation of 1.22, described as "low."

Table 1

<i>Level of Parental Influence</i>				
Item	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Do you feel you are likely to do what your parent(s)/guardian(s) say?	3.63	1.19	High
2.	Have your parent(s)/guardian(s) talked to you about not drinking?	3.60	1.44	High
3.	Have you been open and honest with your parent(s)/guardian(s) about your decision to consume or not to consume alcohol?	3.36	1.40	High
4.	Do you feel that your parent(s)/guardian(s) are likely to influence your decisions?	3.02	1.29	Moderate
5.	Have your parent(s)/guardian(s) expressed strong feelings against your drinking?	2.85	1.49	Moderate
6.	How often do you drink alcohol at home?	1.99	1.09	Low
7.	Do you buy alcoholic beverages frequently?	1.83	1.22	Low
Category Mean		2.90	0.79	Moderate

Legend:

Scale	Limits	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Always	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Often	High
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
2	1.81-2.60	Rarely	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Very low

B. Descriptive Results of Peer Pressure

Table 2 presents the level of peer pressure of the respondents with a total mean of 2.23 and a standard deviation of 0.88, described as "never." This suggests that the level of peer pressure of the students of San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT) is "low." If observed individually, the item that stated, "If my best friend offered an alcoholic drink, it would be hard for me to say no," got the highest mean of 2.49 with a standard deviation of 1.36, described as "low." On the other hand, "If I drink alcohol, other people would think I am "cool," got the lowest mean of 1.68 with a standard deviation of 0.95, also described as "very low."

Table 2

<i>Level of Peer Pressure</i>				
Item	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	I felt pressured to get drunk at parties.	2.38	1.27	Low
2.	I drink alcohol to forget my problems.	2.01	1.24	Low
3.	At times, I have drunk alcohol because my friends urged me to.	2.48	1.27	Low
4.	If my friends are drinking, it would be hard for me to resist having a drink	2.47	1.30	Low
5.	If my best friend offered an alcoholic drink, it would be hard for me to say no.	2.49	1.36	Low
6.	I often feel pressured to drink when I normally would not drink.	2.41	1.25	Low
7.	If I drink alcohol, it will improve my interpersonal relationships.	2.10	1.26	Low
8.	I cannot refuse when my friends offer me a glass of alcoholic drinks because I am afraid of hurting their feelings.	2.18	1.22	Low
9.	If I do not drink alcohol, others may think I am unreliable.	2.11	1.23	Low
10.	If I drink alcohol, other people would think I am "cool".	1.68	0.95	Low
Overall Mean		2.23	0.88	Low

Legend:

Scale	Limits	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Always	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Often	High
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
2	1.81-2.60	Rarely	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Very low

C. Descriptive Results of Alcohol use

Table 3 displays the level of alcohol use of the respondents with a total mean of 2.06 and a standard deviation of 0.01, described as "less than monthly," which means low. When evaluated independently, the item, "How often do you go out to drink alcoholic beverages with friends in the past year?" got the highest mean of 2.31, with a standard deviation of 1.18, interpreted as "low."

Table 3

Level of Alcohol Use

Item Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. How often do you go out to drink alcoholic beverages with friends in the past year?	2.31	1.18	Low
2. How often do you take six or more drinks on one occasion?	2.15	1.20	Low
3. How often have you had a feeling of guilt or remorse during the last year after drinking?	2.10	1.18	Low
4. How often have you found that you could not stop drinking once you had started during the last year?	2.05	1.24	Low
5. How often does a relative friend express concern about your drinking or suggest you cut it down?	2.05	1.23	Low
6. How often have you failed to do what was normally expected of you because of drinking during the last year?	2.03	1.11	Low
7. How often do you miss days of work, school, or other important obligations because of drinking?	2.01	1.27	Low
8. How often have you felt that you should cut down on your drinking during the last year?	2.00	1.17	Low
9. How often during the last year where you were unable to remember what happened the night before because you have been drinking?	1.98	1.28	Low
10. How often do you drink alcoholic beverages when you are by yourself?	1.93	1.10	Low
Category Mean	2.06	1.01	Low

Legend:

Scale	Limits	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Daily or almost daily	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Weekly	High
3	2.61-3.40	Monthly	Moderate
2	1.81-2.60	Less than monthly	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Very low

In the meantime, "How often do you drink alcoholic beverages when you are by yourself?" got the lowest mean of 1.93, with a standard deviation of 1.10, interpreted as "low."

D. Correlation Analysis between Parental Influence, Peer Pressure, and Alcohol use.

Table 4 presents the correlation analysis between the independent and dependent variables of the study. The finding shows that the correlation coefficient of parental influence is .504** and peer pressure is .785**, with p-values of 0.000 being lesser than 0.001 (2-tailed) levels of significance. This simply means that parental influence and peer pressure are significantly associated with alcohol use. Therefore, the first null hypothesis, "There is no significant relationship between parental influence, peer pressure, and alcohol use," is rejected.

Table 4

Correlation Analysis between Parental Influence, Peer Pressure and Alcohol Use

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: Alcohol Use		
	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Parental Influence	.504**	0.000	Significant
Peer pressure	.785**	0.000	Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

E. Regression Analysis between Parental Influence, Peer Pressure, and Alcohol use.

Established in Table 5 is the result of the test of influence conducted between parental influence, peer pressure, and alcohol use. The result revealed that the F-value of 93.845 and the p-value of 0.000 is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that in both collective and individual measurements, parental influence and peer pressure significantly influenced alcohol use. Consequently, the second null hypothesis, "Parental influence and peer pressure do not influence alcohol use," is rejected.

Table 5

Regression Analysis between Parental Influence, Peer Pressure, and Alcohol use

Indicators	Alcohol Used				
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.565	0.238	2.372	0.020	_____
Parental Influence	0.289	0.082	0.227	3.510	0.001 Significant
Peer Pressure	0.801	0.075	0.694	10.744	0.000 Significant
R		.812 ^a	p		0.000 ^b
R ²		.652	S		0.598
F		93.85			

*p<.05

Moreover, the R-square value of 0.659 implies that 65.9 percent of the variance of college students' parental influence and peer pressure is attributed to and can be explained by alcohol use. This likewise denotes that 34.1 percent of the variance can be attributed to factors not covered in this study. Thus, the computed S-value of 0.598 measures the accuracy of the prediction. The smaller its value, the better.

IV. DISCUSSION AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

➤ *Level of Parental Influence*

The moderate level of parental influence among college students is due to the low to high ratings given by the majority of the respondents towards the parental influence item questionnaire. The result indicates that most college students generally follow the decisions of their parents to be more open or honest about drinking and not drinking alcohol. Moreover, it influences their decisions because they occasionally observe how their parents react and express strong feelings against drinking, resulting in rare instances of buying or drinking alcoholic beverages. This result corroborated the finding of several authors [2] [9] who mentioned that parents who enforce strict alcohol consumption rules help their children disengage in alcohol use. On the other hand, parents' involvement in their children's lives includes; communicating openly, modeling responsible behavior, and providing guidance and support that can help to reduce their children's risk of alcohol use and abuse [10].

➤ *Level of Peer Influence*

The overall level of peer pressure among college students is low. Despite being judged as weak, unreliable, uncool, and not getting along with peers, the findings suggest that students can decline their peers' offers to drink alcoholic beverages because they are unpressured, do not feel compelled, and are not afraid of rejection. Some authors suggest that it may be challenging to resist peer pressure, especially when declining invitations could harm your relationships or social standing. However, selecting someone who wants to be associated with them carefully can help to prevent this [1] [15]. Students can repel peer pressure, especially if they possess a high level of self-confidence and self-esteem [18] [34], have solid parental guidance and support [19], have a strong identity and purpose [20] [21], and being educated about the danger and consequences of intense alcohol use [22] [23].

➤ *Level of Alcohol use*

In terms of alcohol use, the results showed that college students have a low level of alcohol consumption. This means that students drink alcohol for less than a month. The result further denotes that most of the San Agustin Institute of Technology college students are not heavy drinkers. The result is somewhat expected since the school usually holds campaigns and awareness about the negative effect of excessive alcohol use. Most schools discourage alcohol consumption since students must prioritize their academic or career goals over alcohol consumption, recognizing that excessive drinking can interfere with their ability to perform well in school [28] [29]. Due to this awareness, the student is reminded and becomes mindful of the negative consequences of irresponsible drinking alcohol. On the other hand, most Filipino college students depend on their parents [30]. Therefore, the majority of the students follow the decision of their parents, specifically if they enforce strict alcohol consumption. Parents are aware of the negative effect of excessive alcohol use on their health and

are concerned about the risks of alcohol-related injuries, accidents, or illnesses. Parents want to protect their children's health and well-being, affecting their alcohol use intention [19].

Numerous studies showed that college students drink alcohol, and some engage in binge drinking, which is to the extent of consuming a large amount of alcohol in a short amount of time with the intention of becoming intoxicated [15] [36]. However, some college students choose not to drink alcohol or drink only in moderation for various reasons. For instance, some students may hold personal or religious beliefs that prohibit or discourage alcohol consumption [31], while others may be concerned about the negative health effects of alcohol [2] [9]. Furthermore, negative experiences, such as blacking out, getting into trouble with the law, or causing harm to themselves or others, may also lead some students to abstain from alcohol [32]. Additionally, some students may prioritize academic or career goals over alcohol consumption, recognizing that excessive drinking can hinder academic performance or job prospects [33]. Finally, students with strong support networks of friends and family who do not consume alcohol may be less likely to drink themselves [10].

➤ *The Significant Association and Impact of Parental Influence on Alcohol use.*

One of the major objectives of the study is to examine the significant relationship and impact of parental influence on alcohol use. When using the test of a relationship, the finding showed that there is a positive link between parental influence and alcohol use. As examined using regression analysis, parental influence significantly affects the alcohol use of college students. The findings recommended that the low-level alcohol consumption of college students is linked with or could contribute to their parents' expression or reaction against drinking and how these parents communicate with their children (e.g., asking them to be more honest about drinking alcohol and demanding them not to drink). The results are indeed supported by the proposition of several experts [2] [10] [11] [13] who statistically found an association between parental influence on alcohol use. The result further suggests that parental influence is a critical factor in the development of alcohol use among college students. It highlights the importance of parents' role in modeling responsible drinking behaviors and providing guidance and support to their children regarding alcohol use. The existing literature supported the result. A study found that non-authoritative parenting style and parental drunkenness contribute to binge drinking among young individuals [2].

In non-authoritarian types of parenting, children may usually feel a lack of emotional support and guidance from their parents, which can lead to feelings of rebellion, defiance, and a desire to seek out risky behaviors such as binge drinking. Further, parental drunkenness can also contribute to binge drinking among young individuals. Parents who regularly engage in heavy drinking or drunkenness may be more likely to perceive alcohol use as

normal or acceptable behavior among children and may be more likely to engage in binge drinking themselves [2].

On the other hand, some authors likewise proved that parental alcohol-related problems [11], parental communication [10], and parental monitoring [13] is associated with the intention and excessive alcohol use among adolescent. Parents need to be aware of the potential impact of their parenting style and their alcohol use on their children's behavior and health outcomes [2]. Open and honest communication, setting clear expectations and boundaries, and providing emotional support and guidance can all be effective ways for parents to help prevent binge drinking and other risky behaviors among their children [10] [13].

➤ *The Significant Association and Influence of Peer Pressure on Alcohol use.*

Another important study objective is to ascertain the significant correlation and influence of peer pressure on alcohol use among college students. Through the test of correlation analysis, the result reveals an association between peer pressure and alcohol use. Upon using regression analysis, the data also showed that peer pressure significantly influenced alcohol use among college students. The finding confirms that when students know how to resist pressure from their peers, they will be able to prevent excessive alcohol consumption. Students who resist peer pressure are less likely to engage in alcohol use [22] [23]. In addition, when students resist peer pressure, they are more likely to make their own decisions and stand up for what they believe in rather than simply going along with what their peers are doing [16] [17]. This can lead to healthier behaviors, including less alcohol use or even abstaining from alcohol altogether [1]. The results support the recent findings of Studer et al. [7] who discovered that positive peer involvement and peer conformity lessen alcohol consumption.

Subsequently, peer pressure related to misconduct [16] [17] and peer delinquency [24] contributes to intense alcohol use. Peer pressure can be a powerful influence, especially on college students, when social acceptance is important. Students may feel pressure to drink alcohol to fit in with their peers, even if they do not want to or feel uncomfortable doing so. While drinking alcohol can be a common and enjoyable social activity that may help reduce stress, it can also be dangerous if not approached responsibly. To avoid it, selecting wisely the peers you associate with can be helpful [15].

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, San Agustin Institute of Technology college students perceived a moderate level of parental influence, low peer pressure, and low alcohol consumption. Further, parental influence and peer pressure showed a significant association with alcohol use when assessed using correlational analysis. When regressed, parental influence and peer pressure significantly predict alcohol use. Thus, it is worth mentioning that students' drinking patterns are

shaped and manifested by their social interactions with peers and parents.

The finding of the study validates the social learning theory of Albert Bandura [35]. The theory suggests that individuals learn behavior through observation, imitation, and reinforcement from their social environment, including parents and peers. Furthermore, the theory posits that behavior is influenced not only by the direct reinforcement of that behavior but also by the observation and modeling of others. Regarding alcohol use, parental influence can be a key factor in shaping attitudes and beliefs about alcohol. Children may observe their parents drinking alcohol and learn to associate alcohol use with relaxation, pleasure, and socializing. Additionally, parents who model responsible drinking behavior and emphasize the risks associated with excessive alcohol use may help to shape their children's attitudes towards alcohol.

On the other hand, peer pressure can also play a significant role in shaping attitudes toward alcohol use. Adolescents are particularly susceptible to the influence of their peers and may be motivated to engage in alcohol use to fit in or be accepted by their peers. Social norms surrounding alcohol use among peer groups can also shape individual attitudes and behaviors. According to social learning theory, these various influences shape an individual's behavior [35]. Overall, social learning theory suggests that parental influence and peer pressure can significantly affect an individual's alcohol use behavior. Parental influence and peer pressure may operate in complementary or conflicting ways, and the strength of these influences may vary depending on the individual and their social environment.

Considering the limitations, the study's findings add significant evidence to previous studies about alcohol use in college students and the effects of parental influence and peer pressure. Additionally, the study includes only private catholic school college students. Therefore, more research is needed to expand the scope of this investigation. A similar study might also be conducted among public and non-Catholic private schools using different methodological techniques, contexts, and participants. With this, a comparison can be made for confirmation or otherwise.

As for prevention and intervention, schools must continue to host alcohol abuse awareness to educate and dissuade them from excessive drinking. Further, promoting good and solid relationships, quality parental communication, and good parental support and monitoring is an avenue to prevent college students from alcohol abuse. Lastly, seminars on resisting peer pressure and activities may help students gain confidence about their choices and themselves.

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